

Purchase Behavior of Green Products among Nepali Consumers

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to examine the role of attitude on purchase behavior towards green products among Nepali consumers. Under quantitative study, cross-sectional research design is adopted. Data has been collected from 388 Nepali consumers of the Chitwan District aged between 20 and 40 employing purposive sampling technique.

Results generated from Structural Equation Modeling indicated that green consumption value has a positive significant impact on attitude towards green products, reasons for and against purchasing green products while negative insignificant impact was confirmed between reason for and against purchasing green products on attitude towards green products. It has also been found that attitude towards green product significantly impact purchase behavior.

This study emphasises the potentiality of win-win situation where consumer preferences cannot only meet their desires but also contribute to sustainable environment.

Keywords: *attitude, green products, purchase behavior*